

CALIBRATION OF INFRARED STRESS MEASUREMENT TECHNIQUE FOR CFRP COMPOSITES AND ITS APPLICATION

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SUMMARY : Infrared stress measurement technique is applied as a method of non-destructive evaluation of composites with advantages of in-situ and non-contact nature. Thermo-elastic constants of unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced plastics (UD-CFRP) needed for quantitative measurements are obtained through the infrared stress graphic system. The theoretical thermo-elastic constants are derived through the basic equations and physical properties of constituent materials, which are compared with the experimental values. As a consequence, a reliability of the measured thermo-elastic constants is established and capability of this system for quantitative stress measurement is shown. It is also demonstrated that temperature dependency of a transverse coefficient of thermal expansion and a specific heat at constant stress of UD-CFRP cancel each other so as to decrease temperature dependency of the thermo-elastic constant. Other influential factors on measurements like a frequency effect are also examined.

KEYWORDS: thermo-elastic constant, non-destructive evaluation, coefficient of thermal expansion, specific heat, density, surface temperature, stress amplitude.

INTRODUCTION

The infrared stress measurement is a technique that the reversible temperature change at the surface of a body is measured precisely by an infrared sensor and it is transformed to the stress change. The temperature change is caused by the thermo-elastic effect, or in other words, coupled thermo-elasticity in adiabatic continua. Two experimental key points are to obtain a precise temperature signal in a very small amplitude and to correlate a temperature change to the applied force. The recent measurement system consists of a digital signal thermo-camera with graphic software as a core device. The system used here is referred to as an infrared stress graphic system (ISGS). This technique has been applied to metallic materials and composites not only as stress measurement but also as a non-destructive evaluation (NDE) method. It is featured by the following two intrinsic advantages, in-situ and non-contact natures. These advantages will be enhanced particularly in structural tests. A coefficient by which temperature change is transformed into stress, the thermo-elastic coefficient (TEC) so referred to here, is well established for metallic materials. In spite of its high expense as a NDE device, a few types of ISGSs have been spread gradually into applied mechanics fields.

Several efforts have been conducted for application of this technique to composites^{2)~4)}. It is known that the measured results for carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) laminates depend on almost solely transverse stress due to its orthotropic thermal expansion nature¹⁾. Therefore, there is no need to separate stress components and it is considered to be an advantage in composite measurement. However, the TEC in CFRP measurement is not as reliable as in metal, at least to the author knowledge. Once the TEC of CFRP is established, the measurement is considered to be easier than metal cases experimentally.

The aim of this paper is to raise a reliability of the TEC of uni-directional (UD) CFRP. For that purpose, the measured TEC through the used ISGS was calibrated using the governing formula and three basic material properties measured as accurately as possible. They are the coefficients of thermal expansion, the specific heat at constant stress and density, which govern TEC. The coefficients of thermal expansion were obtained by a thermal expansion measuring device using laser interferometry. Two other experimental check points, the dependency on loading frequency and the line accumulation numbers in the current ISGS as user's selection, were also examined. Consequently, the fundamentals of quantitative stress measurement technique for CFRP laminates are established.

SPECIMENS AND THE MATERIAL CONSTANTS

Table 1 Physical Property and V_f of Constituents of T400H/#3631

E_{fr}	187.0 GPa ^{\$}	E_m	3.63GPa [#]
$\kappa (=E_{fr}/E_{fz})$	0.084 ^{\$\$}	ν_m	0.38 ^{**}
ν_{frz}	0.3 [*]	α_m	$5.21 \times 10^{-5}/K$ ^{&}
$\nu_{fr\theta}$	0.42 [*]	ρ_m	$1.29 \times 10^3 kg/m^3$ [#]
α_{fr}	$7.6 \times 10^{-6}/K$ [*]	$C_{m\sigma}$	$1.294 \times 10^3 Nm/(kgK)$ ^{##}
α_{fz}	$-7.8 \times 10^{-7}/K$ [*]		
ρ_f	$1.82 \times 10^3 kg/m^3$ [#]		
$C_{f\sigma}$	$0.7635 \times 10^3 Nm/(kgK)$ [#]	V_f	0.577 ^{&}

\$ Ref. 4); \$\$ Estimated data from Ref. 4), 5); * Ref. 6).
 & Measured data in this paper; ** Ref. 6); 828 epoxy data.
 # Ref. 7); ## Ref. 7); #3900-2 epoxy data.

Specimens used in this paper were fabricated with prepregs P1211-15: T400H carbon fiber / #3631 epoxy resin by TORAY Industries, Inc. Dimensions of specimens in mm were 220 x 25^w x 1^t for 0 UD- CFRP, 220 x 12.5^w x 6^t for 45 UD- CFRP and 200 x 25^w x 6^t for 90 UD- CFRP. Both ends of 0 UD-CFRP specimens were protected with tapered GFRP tabs whereas the 45 and 90 UD-CFRP specimens were not protected. In the measurement of the coefficients of thermal expansion, small blocks were cut out from the 0 and 90 UD-CFRP specimens so as to be about 10 mm in length. The both ends of these blocks were ground to be spherical in order to realize point contact to the optical interference plates. The length of blocks were measured precisely with a micrometer. Material constants of this T400H/#3631 system used in this paper are shown in Table 1. Note that some of these values were measured in this paper and the other values were taken from references as footnotes of the Table 1.

THE BASIC THEORY OF INFRARED STRESS MEASUREMENT

It is commonly known that a temperature change is caused by pressure variation in gaseous media under adiabatic conditions. In parallel to gas, it is also caused by stress in solid continua. However, since the temperature change is often very small in the case of solid, it

cannot be observed easily. The temperature change phenomenon in a elastic body under adiabatic conditions is referred to as the thermo-elastic effect in this paper. It is reasonably considered that the temperature change is a reversible process and is basically different phenomenon from the non-reversible temperature change with a visco-elastic nature and internal friction. In an isotropic body, the temperature change amplitude, dT , becomes proportional to the sum of principal stresses on the surface., $d\sigma_i$. However, in an orthotropic body, like CFRP, the basic constitutive equation and its coefficients have to be examined.

In the plane stress state, the temperature change in an orthotropic continuum as UD-CFRP by the thermo-elastic effect is described by Kageyama¹⁾ as the next equation:

$$dT = -\frac{T}{\rho \cdot C_\sigma} (\alpha_L \cdot d\sigma_L + \alpha_T \cdot d\sigma_T) \quad (1)$$

where

dT : Temperature variation amplitude by cyclic stresses,

T : Background temperature (in Kelvin),

ρ : Density,

C_σ : Specific heat at constant stress,

α : Coefficient of thermal expansion,

$d\sigma$: Cyclic stress amplitude,

and where the subscripts, L and T , indicate longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively. In order to simplify Eq. (1), two constants are defined as follows:

$$K_L = \frac{\alpha_L}{\rho \cdot C_\sigma} \quad (2)$$

$$K_T = \frac{\alpha_T}{\rho \cdot C_\sigma} \quad (3)$$

These K s are designated as thermo-elastic constants (TEC) connecting the temperature and the stress variation. Then Eq. (1) is rewritten as:

$$dT = -T(K_L \cdot d\sigma_L + K_T \cdot d\sigma_T) \quad (4)$$

The temperature variation by stress in the longitudinal direction is relatively very small value due to very small TEC in the longitudinal direction which will be examined again in this paper. Taking account of this fact, the measured stress change is almost governed by the transverse stress change on the surface of a body. Hence, Eq. (4) can be approximated into:

$$dT \cong -K_T \cdot T \cdot d\sigma_T \quad (5)$$

Namely, a measurement of the temperature change amplitude in time average provides the transverse stress change amplitude on the surface with an aid of K_T .

NOTES IN ACTUAL MEASUREMENT

In this section, the actual situation of the measurement through the present ISGS will be explained and some important remarks will be stated. A schematic illustration of the temperature and stress history is shown in Fig. 1 for the case of tensile loading. It should be noted first that the loading must be in constant frequency with a constant amplitude in order to obtain a precise time-average of a temperature amplitude. There exist a lower limit of

frequency to satisfy an eventual adiabatic condition, which will be mentioned later. It can be considered that the temperature change off the loading frequency caused by the background atmosphere or visco-elasticity does not affect the generated temperature change by a loading cycles as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Schematic Description of the Measurement in Temperature and Load Histories

The other purpose of this paper is to check this phenomena. The used ISGS system here was JTG-8000 made by JEOL Co. LTD in JAPAN. The surface of the specimens were painted in black in order to increase the infrared emission. This effect will be taken into account later. The temperature change was scanned in the horizontal direction by an oscillating mirror in 400 Hz in this system. It will be accumulated and averaged in order to improve a S/N ratio. This procedure is referred to as Line Accumulation in the present ISGS system. As a next procedure, a vertical scanning by the other oscillating mirror creates a two dimensional temperature distribution image of the object surface. This procedure is also repeatedly done for a better S/N ratio, being referred to as Frame Accumulation. Because a total measuring time is roughly governed by Frame Accumulation numbers and total accumulation number affecting quality of image is defined by a multiple of Frame and Line Accumulation numbers, the idea of Line Accumulation is conceived in order to reduce measuring time. Number of Line Accumulation is under operator's definition. He has to make an optimum trade-off between image quality and measuring time.

However, one important point of caution for quantitative measurement exists concerning this Line Accumulation number. An upper part of Fig. 1 should be referred for explanation of this situation where two examples of single (suffix 1) and four (suffix 4) Line Accumulation numbers are given. Suppose that the temperature change at a certain point on the scanned line becomes a sinusoidal curve as shown. Four times of accumulation are done in a loading cycle and an average is assumed to be a temperature peak (or bottom). In the actual measurement, temperature difference dT is determined by a digital operation in a system computer. So, if we compare dT for two cases, it can be understood naturally that dT_1 is always larger than dT_4 and that dT_1 should be maximal if the peak and bottom temperature points are correctly captured. Hence, single Line Accumulation number must be chosen in the system for

quantitative measurement. Although number 4 was erroneously used by the authors in the earlier measurement, those results were not used in the present quantitative discussion. The other point of caution for quantitative measurement is a simple factor, optical cleanness in the lens system for which periodical maintenance is required.

Because an actual procedure is going on as above in the system, the loading must be applied to the specimen in a manner of constant amplitude and frequency. Such loading can be applied by a hydraulic fatigue testing machine, Instron type 8501, of 100 kN capacity. Other loading conditions are tension-tension with 0.1 stress ratio and 5Hz sine wave. It should be also noted that a phase shift between stress peak and temperature bottom happens usually although an elementary theory tells us no phase shift. From the viewpoint of hardware, this system uses the feedback of the loading signals to determine the measurement timing. For the determining the actual phase shift, some preliminary trial is needed.

MEASURED RESULTS OF THE THERMO-ELASTIC CONSTANTS WITH UD-CFRP AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 2 Relationships between dT and $d\sigma_x$

The temperature change dT was measured by this system to define the TEC of CFRP under the stress $d\sigma_x$ under the loading limitation, where x denotes loading direction. The averages of surface temperature changes in a certain area defined out of the edge effect zone are plotted in Fig. 2 as a function of the applied stress for the 90 UD-CFRP specimens. Figure 2 contains both the previous results by 4 times Line Accumulations and the recent results by single Line Accumulation, which are indicated by subscripts (4) and (1), respectively. These results lead to the following relations between dT and $d\sigma$ through the least square method.

$$dT_{(4)} = -6.07 \times 10^{-9} d\sigma_T \tag{6}$$

$$dT_{(1)} = -6.58 \times 10^{-9} d\sigma_T \tag{7}$$

These relations and measured background temperature of $T=298[K]$ were substituted into Eq. (5) and the TECs were obtained as follows:

$$K_{T(4)} = 2.04 \times 10^{-11} [1/\text{Pa}] \quad (8)$$

$$K_{T(1)} = 2.21 \times 10^{-11} [1/\text{Pa}] \quad (9)$$

Because these values were obtained for the 90 UD-CFRP, Eq. (5) is considered to be exact. The 0 and 45 UD-CFRP specimens were also similarly measured in the same condition as previous series of test and their results are plotted in Fig. 2 for confirming approximation of Eq. (5). If the results of the 45 UD-CFRP are transformed into a transverse stress amplitude, an almost similar coefficient to Eq. (6) can be obtained. In the case of the 0 UD-CFRP, the following TEC, K_L , was obtained in the same manner as the 90 UD-CFRP owing to $d\sigma_T = 0$.

$$K_L = -1.16 \times 10^{-13} [1/\text{Pa}] \quad (10)$$

However, it is needed later that the K_T and K_L must be calibrated with infrared emissivity of the black paint on the surface of the specimens, for increasing infrared emissivity. In practical situations, the thermo-elastic effect of the 0 UD-CFRP are negligible due to the same order of measurement errors because of its material properties. Thus, the approximation of Eq. (5) is regarded as confirmed.

DETERMINATION OF THERMO-ELASTIC CONSTANTS THROUGH THE OTHER PHYSICAL ROUTE

The TECs were theoretically calculated in this section using the basic physical law and experimentally obtained material constants in order to validate the measured TECs by the

ISGS. If density, ρ , specific heat under constant stress, C_σ , and coefficients of thermal expansion, α_T and α_L , are known for UD-CFRP, the TECs, K_T and K_L , are obtained by substituting them into Eqs. (2) and (3). Physical properties, ρ and C_σ , of a UD-CFRP are given as follows if it contains no void and if all constituent ρ and C_σ are known:

$$\rho = V_f \cdot \rho_f + (1 - V_f) \cdot \rho_m \quad (11)$$

$$C_\sigma = V_f \cdot C_{f\sigma} \cdot \frac{\rho_f}{\rho} + (1 - V_f) \cdot C_{m\sigma} \cdot \frac{\rho_m}{\rho} \quad (12)$$

where subscripts f and m denote fiber and matrix respectively. Instead of Eq. (11), the following value of ρ measured with small pieces cut out of the TEC specimens by using a precision balance, was adopted in the present calculation:

$$\rho = 1.5692 \times 10^3 [\text{kg/m}^3] \quad (13)$$

The physical property, C_σ , was also measured through a type of calorimeter, SH-3000 made by Shinku-Rikoh LTD, JAPAN, with an assistance of a specialist company. The obtained results of C_σ for two specimens are shown in Fig. 3 where a solid line indicates the average. Because the results show temperature dependency, the following value of C_σ at 25 °C is specified as the average between 20 °C and 30 °C, and employed in this paper:

a) Overview,

b) Detail around Specimen

Fig. 4 Pictures of Thermal Expansion Measuring Device by Laser Interferometry: LIX-1

$$C_{\sigma} = 9.77 \times 10^2 \text{ [Nm/(kgK)]} \quad (14)$$

If we admit the material properties in Table 1 and Eq. (13), the following C_{σ} is calculated only for a reference:

$$C_{\sigma} = 9.60 \times 10^2 \text{ [Nm/(kgK)]} \quad (15)$$

Fig. 3 Measured Results of Specific Heat for T400H/#3631 at Constant Stress

The rest material properties, α_T and α_L , are required to be precisely measured according to the above consideration, and some experimental details are described here. The used equipment was a thermal expansion measurement machine using laser interferometry: LIX-1 made by Shinku-Riko LTD., JAPAN. An overview picture of this machine and a specimen setting detail are shown in Fig. 4. The specimens were initially refrigerated below -10 °C by liquid nitrogen and heated over 100 °C at the rate of 3 °C/mm. The refrigeration was aimed to obtain precise dependency of CTE around the room temperature. Expansion of the specimens within each 10 °C was primarily obtained and it was transformed into the α_T and α_L . Values of α_T and α_L at the central temperature point of the segment were regarded as a representative in that segment. The obtained results of 90 UD-CFRP, α_T , are plotted by a symbol and the average of six specimens are indicated by a dashed curve in Fig. 5. The obtained data were

based on second and third measurement because a hygroscopic effect on CTE is expected strongly in the first heating. The α_L of 0 UD-CFRP were also obtained and plotted in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 Measured Results of CTE: 0 UD-CFRP

Fig. 5 Measured Results of CTE: 90 UD-CFRP

Because the temperature point at actual measurements of the TECs was 25°C, the values of α_T and α_L at 25 °C were determined as follows from Fig. 5:

$$\alpha_T = 3.680 \times 10^{-5} [1/K] \tag{16}$$

$$\alpha_L = -1.280 \times 10^{-8} [1/K] \tag{17}$$

If we substitute material properties of Eqs. (16), (17) and Table 1 into Eqs. (2), (3), (13) and (14), we have the following TECs:

$$K_T = 2.40 \times 10^{-11} [1/Pa] \tag{18}$$

$$K_L = -8.35 \times 10^{-14} [1/\text{Pa}] \quad (19)$$

In comparison with Eq. (9), Eq. (18) shows close but slightly larger value of K_T . One reason of this tendency can be ascribed to an influence of the emissivity on the surface at infrared stress measurement. It was already measured⁹⁾ that the used black paint has the emissivity value of 0.96 within the present infrared sensor range. The coefficient in Eq. (9) based on 1 Line Accumulation can be modified into the following value:

$$K_T = 2.30 \times 10^{-11} [1/\text{Pa}] \quad (20)$$

It is indicated that Eq. (20) is only 4 % lower than a value of Eq. (18). The result of 4 Line Accumulations does not agree so well with Eq. (18). Further pursuit of the reasons of the difference between Eqs. (18) and (20) is skipped in this paper. Some suspicious factors are nominated as: an imperfection in finding the ideal phase shift, irregularity in temperature variation and so on. From above discussions, it can be concluded at least that the K_T obtained by the infrared stress measurement system exhibits high reliability.

If we compare Figs. 3 and 5, it is clear that both α_T and C_σ show temperature dependencies and that they are expected to cancel out each other by virtue of Eq. (3). Actually, it is demonstrated that temperature dependency disappears in TECs as follows:

$$\alpha_T = 4.181 \times 10^{-5} [1/\text{K}] \quad (21)$$

$$C_\sigma = 11.53 \times 10^2 [\text{Nm}/(\text{kgK})] \quad (22)$$

These values give the following K_T :

$$K_T = 2.31 \times 10^{-11} [1/\text{Pa}] \quad (23)$$

We also need to examine temperature dependency of ρ . By CTE data, ρ at 80 °C is estimated to be only 0.4% smaller than at 25 °C, being negligible in Eq. (23). A trivial temperature dependency of K_T is an importance and an advantage for the quantitative infrared stress measurement around the room temperature.

On the other hand, Eq. (10) can be revised by taking account the infrared emissivity as follows:

$$K_L = -1.21 \times 10^{-13} [1/\text{Pa}] \quad (24)$$

If we compare this value with Eq. (19), it is found that an agreement seems not to be favorable. However, an order of discrepancy between two values is very small if we consider the both measurements were done at the fringe of assured accuracy of the testing systems.

COMMENTS OF OTHER INFLUENTIAL FACTORS FOR MEASURING THE THERMO-ELASTIC CONSTANTS

The infrared stress measurement was done under loading frequency of 5 Hz in this paper unless otherwise stated. The characteristics of loading frequency effect should be discussed here. Hence, the temperature changes were measured under various frequencies for 90 UD-CFRP and 45 UD-CFRP with the same loading amplitude. The results of these trials are shown in Fig. 7 with almost no effect around 5 Hz. Thus, it is verified that measurement at 5 Hz is appropriate. It should be noticed that the data in this figure are the results of 4 times Line Accumulations.

It is a well-known fact that there may be an influence of internal moisture on the coefficient of thermal expansion. For the examination of this influence, the TEC of 90 UD-CFRP was immediately measured after desiccation by a drier at 100 °C air for ten days. However, no clear evidence of the hygroscopic effect on the TEC could be found.

Fig. 7 Load Frequency Effects on Temperature Amplitude

APPLICATION TO DELAMINATION IN CF/EPOXY LAMINATE

Finally, an practical ISGS application of this to composite NDE is described in this section. Quasi-isotropic [(45/-45/0/90)sym.] coupon specimens of 8-ply of CFRP (T400/#3631) laminate were measured under tension - tension cyclic fatigue loading. Free edge delamination starts and propagates during loading for this type of laminates due to Poisson's ratio mismatch. The loading conditions used in the tests in this chapter are as follows; Tension-tension with stress ratio $R=0.1$, load control mode and constant amplitude sine wave of 5 Hz. All surface area of the specimen was inspected by the ISGS and also by a ultrasonic C-scanner at an appropriate interval of loading for comparison. Applied loading level during stress measurements was maintained at a lower level than delamination propagation critical in this area scan. When a ultrasonic C-scan inspection for monitoring delamination propagation is done, specimens were detached from the used hydraulic machine. For a trace purpose of rapidly changing delamination propagation by the ISGS, a line scan inspection was used to reduce a measurement time. It should be noted that measured stress is the stress at the surface normal to the fiber direction.

Stress Measurement C-scan Picture

Fig. 9 A Comparison Measured Stress Pattern with a C-scan Results for CF/Epoxy Coupon Specimen with Edge Delamination

Fig. 8 Measured Results of Transverse Stress on top 45 Layer Surface

Delamination onset and propagation between 0/90 and alternately 90/0 were observed in this fatigue test. These delaminations develop as increasing loading cycles and stop with remained strip of delamination area of 1 ~ 2 mm width. Measured results of stress distribution transverse to the loading direction by the line scan are shown in Fig. 8. In order to clearly indicate C-scan edges and delamination tips symbols of | and ▲ are used in Fig. 8, respectively.

The measured stress pattern obtained by the area scan agrees well with a ultrasonic C-scan delamination image as indicated in Fig. 9. The fact that free edge delaminations liberate surface stresses well plays a key role for such a good correlation. The true delamination pattern in experiments was alternate appearance between in 0/90 and 90/0 interface as mentioned earlier. It can be recognized that width of initial stress plateau is decayed corresponding to delamination propagation and that stresses drop at delamination edges. The stress drop moves inside as the delamination propagates. As a summary, this ISGS system can be used at least as an in-situ mean of non-destructive evaluation for composite laminate if internal damage clearly affects the surface stress state.

CONCLUSIONS

Reliability of TECs for infrared stress measurement is examined and established in comparison with calculated TECs using experimentally determined coefficient of thermal expansion, density and specific heat at constant stress. An excellent correlation between calculated and experimental TECs is achieved if infrared emissivity factor is introduced. Such reliability is required for a quantitative stress measurement of CFRP laminates by using the infrared stress measurement. It is demonstrated that quantitative stress measurement of CFRP by the infrared stress measurement is possible. Also, it is found that the temperature dependency of both the coefficients of thermal expansion and specific heat at a constant stress cancel out each other even at 80 °C. It is a very important advantage for the present stress measurement. No effect of moisture inside the specimens, and insensitivity to loading frequency over 5 Hz were also verified in the present technique. Measurements in one Line Accumulation must be done in order to obtain quantitative result by this system.

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